

Knowledge Creation and Transfer in Family Businesses

Adefunke Olanike Alabi

Department of Library and Information Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Lagos
aalabi@unilag.edu.ng, oladesh@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study examined knowledge creation and transfer in family businesses within a selected local government area of Bariga, Lagos. The study employed a descriptive survey design to collect data from 120 respondents. Using a purposive sampling technique, individuals involved in informal family businesses such as fabric sales, shoemaking, baking/culinary activities, liquid soap production, tailoring/fashion design, and traditional medicine were selected as participants for the study. Data were collected through questionnaire. The data collection lasted for three weeks. Using SPSS version 25, the quantitative data were analysed with frequencies, percentages, weighted means, and standard deviations. The results indicate that knowledge creation and transfer in family business is achieved through mentoring and coaching; observation and apprenticeship; storytelling; and informal interactions. However, with a mean score of 3.28, participants agreed that mentoring is the most commonly used method for knowledge creation and transfer. Respondents emphasized that older family members share valuable tacit knowledge that younger generations find useful in the business, while younger family members are more technologically savvy, thereby helping older generations adapt to modern tools/innovations for the smooth running of the business. Further findings revealed that **generational gaps sometimes create barriers to effective knowledge sharing in family business**. The study concludes that effective knowledge management practices are essential in family businesses to preserve tacit knowledge on one hand, and ensure business continuity.

Keywords: Knowledge management, knowledge creation, knowledge transfer; family business,

Introduction

The success of businesses, be it formal or informal or regardless of ownership, geographical location, type and size, depends on seeing knowledge as an asset that must be stored in a collective organisational memory. Knowledge in businesses is multifaceted, encompassing both explicit and tacit knowledge rooted in traditions, values, and networks (Chaudhary et al., 2025). The field of knowledge management has been popular in the business sector for over two decades because it has consistently been a key force behind advancement and creativity in the business world (Cristache et al., 2025). Knowledge management is conceptualised as an interrelated set of business processes developed in an organisation to create, identify, capture, store, transfer, and apply knowledge (Hayward, 2000; Olubiyi, et al., 2019). In this context, knowledge management in family firms goes beyond merely transferring business skills to the next generation, but thinking proactively about survival, innovation, and succession. Effective knowledge management (KM) protects both explicit (recorded) and tacit (experience-based) information through family councils, mentorship programs, and digital repositories (Kammerlander and König, 2024).

In Nigeria, Africa's largest economy, family businesses dominate the commercial landscape, from small and medium-sized trading enterprises to large, diversified conglomerates (Adegbite et al., 2019). Family businesses operate within a distinctive milieu characterised by strong kinship ties, a collectivist cultural ethos, underdeveloped formal institutions, and a volatile economic environment. Although family businesses account for 80% of Nigeria's employment and more than 60% of its GDP, Nigeria's economic stability is at risk due to inadequate knowledge management

practices (Adegbite et al., 2024). The discourse in literature shows that knowledge management is crucial to an organisation's long-term survival, successful inter-generational knowledge transfer and strong entrepreneurial culture that shapes innovation and risk-taking (Chaudhary, et al., 2025). Studies indicate that nearly 70% of family businesses fail to survive into the second generation, largely due to ineffective succession planning and inadequate transfer of tacit knowledge between generations (Baltazar et al., 2023). There is limited empirical research on knowledge management practices in family businesses in informal settings. This research aims to fill that gap.

Research Objectives

The study was guided by the following research objectives:

1. determine the methods used for knowledge creation and transfer in family businesses
2. ascertain the family dynamics that influence knowledge creation and transfer
3. find out the intergenerational tension impeding knowledge sharing

Literature Review

Sustainable family businesses can be achieved through a culture of knowledge sharing across generations (Woodfield and Husted, 2022). Knowledge in family business can be grouped into three main categories: family knowledge, which encompasses values, relationships, and shared history; business knowledge, which includes operational and technical expertise; and governance knowledge, which relates to ownership structures and board functions (Chirico and Salvato, 2016). Knowledge management is a multidimensional phenomenon that includes knowledge creation, sharing, transfer, integration, and application. Knowledge management is a significant research contexts area the world over that has made tremendous impact in various disciplines (Arzubiaga et. al., 2022). According to Belkhodja (2022), the success of knowledge management in family firms is determined by both the selected KM practices and the firm's inherent characteristics, which govern the **creation, transfer, and strategic application of knowledge** and thereby impact innovation and long-term competitiveness.

According to Belkhodja (2022), the success of knowledge management in family business is determined by both the selected KM practices and the firm's inherent characteristics influence **creation, transfer, and strategic application of knowledge** and thereby impact innovation and long-term competitiveness. Knowledge creation results in the development of new knowledge, new operational methods and new solutions that were not present in the business before. The SECI model sees knowledge creation as a dynamic process across multiple levels (Şener, 2020). It is widely applied in Africa, with socialisation identified as the most impactful stage when supported by knowledge-sharing conditions (Adesina and Ocholla, 2019). In family businesses, there is excessive reliance on the socialisation phase of the SECI model thereby limiting externalisation and weakens knowledge transfer between older and younger generation (Nonaka and von Krogh, 2009; Ge and Campopiano, 2021). Some other scholars such as Bergh et. al. (2025) consider knowledge creation and transfer to function as the primary method that connects family businesses to multigenerational business continuity.

Family businesses use knowledge for two purposes: solving existing problems through small improvements and testing new methods to develop products and operational systems. Knowledge is created by combining predecessors' experience with new external knowledge, such as formal education and exposure in different work settings. Pipatanantakurn and Ractham (2022) found that knowledge transfer in family business takes place during succession and it is a continuous process. The study by Cisneros et. al. (2022) demonstrates that business successors acquire two types of knowledge, which include operational expertise and stakeholder relationship management skills, with a view to sustaining business operations. Yu (2026) argues that succession is both a governance and learning process. In business, there must be established avenues to create and share knowledge. However, bigger family businesses manage knowledge better than small and medium-sized ones (Döring and Witt, 2020).

Dzenopoljac et. al. (2024) highlight that knowledge sharing, particularly tacit, is essential for building both exploitative and explorative capabilities. Exploitative capabilities focus on refining and efficiently using existing knowledge and practices, while explorative capabilities emphasize innovation, learning, and the development of new ideas. Together, these capabilities enable firms to balance stability with adaptability for sustained performance. Knowledge transfer is intertwined with the relationship between family members. Huang, et al. (2023) highlight that knowledge transfer, especially tacit is vital for succession in family businesses because successors leverage business founder's knowledge for innovation, and a supportive culture in open knowledge sharing.

Existing research (Hoon et. al.,2023; Rossignoli et. al., 2024; Pipatanantakurn and Ractham, 2022) identified multiple formal and informal mechanisms as established practices for knowledge transfer in family businesses. These include mentoring and apprenticeship programs; family business meetings; digital documentation; storytelling methods; learning-by-doing; early involvement in the business, joint work with the business owner or founder, external jobs/education, and structured succession stages; documentation and network-based learning.

Pipatanantakurn and Ractham (2022) argue further that knowledge transfer entails a combination of different methods in the transition process. Ramos et al., (2024) assert that knowledge transfer in family business leads to improved performance and competitive advantages. Knowledge transfer in family business is bidirectional in that the younger generations bring creativity, innovation and change (Martínez-Falcó et al., 2026). From a Romanian perspective, family businesses rely on social interactions like mentoring and informal discussions to transfer of tacit knowledge, thereby strengthening trust and family culture. However, this approach risks knowledge loss if key members leave and limits scalability and innovation (Moțoc, 2020). The author argues that balancing socialization with externalisation, that is documenting processes, helps family businesses achieve both stability and growth.

A recent study (Rossignoli et al.,2024) indicates the use of communities of practice (CoP) as knowledge sharing practice in family business. CoP's effectiveness in knowledge sharing depends on leadership approach and consistency around shared values (Rossignoli et al.,2024). The importance of Communities of Practice (CoPs) in knowledge creation and sharing across generations cannot be overemphasized. According to McAdam et al. (2024), family businesses are conceptualised as communities of practice, wherein both family and non-family members engage in collective learning through sustained participation, shared historical context, and collaborative

problem-solving processes. However, ignorance/lack of awareness from both source and recipient, lack of recipient absorptive capacity, causal ambiguity of the knowledge/practice, and difficult relationships between source and recipient act as impediments to knowledge creation and transfer (Szulanski, 1996). Effective knowledge transfer in family businesses requires addressing four key barriers: ignorance/lack of awareness through structured knowledge sharing, strengthening recipient absorptive capacity via mentoring and skill development, reducing causal ambiguity by documenting and explaining the logic of practices, and improving difficult relationships.

Del Vecchio et. al. (2025) examined how younger generations in businesses contribute to the digital transformation and resilience of family businesses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors note that digital transformation yield benefits such as improved competitiveness, decision-making, communication, and value creation across business areas, and that the younger generation played significant role in driving digital innovation and strengthening resilience capabilities.

Subhani et al. (2026) investigated intergenerational challenges in family businesses by focusing on differences between Generation X and Generation Y in innovation, technology use, and succession planning using a qualitative approach among 18 owners of family business. The authors found a clear generational divide that affects family legacy and modernisation approaches. The findings highlight the need for intergenerational dialogue, structured succession planning, and strategic technology adoption to balance tradition with innovation. These studies indicate that the integration of new technologies has increased operational efficiency, enabled more effective marketing strategies, fostered innovation in business models, and facilitated geographic expansion.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive survey design to examine knowledge creation and transfer in family businesses in the informal sector. Family businesses in the informal sector were selected due to their contribution to economic activities and job creation (Ebrahim and van den Berg, 2024). The survey was conducted using a self-administered structured questionnaire to collect quantitative data from 120 respondents in Bariga Local Government Area, Lagos. This local government was selected because it is a commercial setting with numerous family-owned businesses in the informal sector. Purposive sampling was used to select families involved in fabric sales, shoe-making, baking/culinary activities, liquid soap production, tailoring/fashion design, and traditional medicine. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire with two main sections. Section A captured demographic and business characteristics such as gender, age, marital status, education, business type, and year of establishment. Section B has a 4-point Likert scale (from strongly disagree to strongly agree). Before administering the questionnaire, a pilot test of the instrument was conducted with 20 respondents from a population with similar characteristics in the Somolu Local Government area to assess content validity. The Cronbach alpha of 0.81, was obtained indicating satisfactory internal consistency. Participants were duly informed about the purpose of the study, provided informed consent, and participation was voluntary. The data collection lasted for three weeks. SPSS version 25 was used to code and transcribe the gathered data. Data were analysed using frequencies, percentages, weighted mean and standard deviation.

Result

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Results in Table 1 show that more female respondents (56% or 67) participated in the study. This gender distribution indicates that women are more involved in family based, service-oriented, and entrepreneurial economic activities. A majority of the respondents (47% or 56) were between 31-40 years. Results further indicated that many (49 or 40.8%) of the respondents were school certificate holders, followed by HND/OND holders with 37 or 30.8%. Many (64 or 53.3 %) of the businesses have existed for 10 years or more. The data obtained is reliable because the results demonstrated a significant combination across demographic variables. Moreover, these demographic characteristics indicate that the views of the respondents on knowledge creation and transfer are based on real experience rather than assumptions.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents (N = 120)

Demographic Characteristics	Items	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	53	44.0
	Female	67	56.0
Age	18-30 Years	32	26.7
	31-40 Years	56	46.7
	41-50 Years	21	17.5
	51 Years & above	11	9.2
	Marital status	Single	41
Qualification	Married	71	34.2
	Divorced/Separated	8	6.7
	BSc Degree	32	26.7
	SSCE	49	40.8
	HND/OND	37	30.8
Types of Family Business	Primary Sch. Leaving Cert.	5	4.2
	Liquid soap production	29	24.2
	Tailoring/Fashion design	14	11.7
	Baking, Culinary	41	34.2
	Traditional Medicine	15	12.5
When was the business established	Fabric Sales	21	17.5
	>10 years	64	53.0
	< 5 years	56	47.0

Source: Field data, 2025

Table 2 presents the various methods used for knowledge creation and transfer in family businesses. Findings show that knowledge is transferred in family business using mentoring and coaching; observation and apprenticeship; storytelling; and informal interactions. However, with a mean score of 3.28, participants agreed that mentoring and coaching is the most commonly used method for knowledge transfer. This was closely followed by informal interaction with mean score of 3.24.

Table 2: Methods used for Knowledge creation and transfer

S/N	Knowledge transfer methods	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std.	Rank
1	Mentoring and coaching	100 83.3%	9 7.5%	8 6.7%	3 2.5%	3.28	0.62	1
2	Observation and apprenticeship	86 71.7%	10 83.3%	4 3.3%	20 16.7%	3.11	1.03	3
3	Story telling	55 45.83%	38 31.67%	16 13.3%	11 9.2%	3.11	0.91	3
4.	Informal interactions	46 38.33%	55 45.83%	12 10.0%	7 5.84%	3.24	0.84	2

Source: Field data, 2025. Note: Std. Dev = standard deviation; Criterion mean = 2.50. Items with mean scores of 2.50 or above were accepted.

As regards family dynamics influencing knowledge creation and transfer, findings in Table 3 with mean = 3.38 indicated that participants agreed that older family members share valuable traditional knowledge that younger generations find useful in the business. A majority (111 or 92.3%) of the participants agreed that younger family members contribute technological/digital skills that help older generations adapt to modern tools/innovations in the smooth running of the business. This indicates that younger family members bring technological innovations and digital skills, therefore, helping the business to remain relevant in a modern environment. Many (78 or 65%) of the respondents affirmed that generational gaps sometimes create barriers to effective knowledge sharing in family business. Moreover, a large number of the respondents (73 or 61%) agreed that differences in education/professional backgrounds among family members enhance collective problem-solving in family business.

Table 3: Family dynamics influencing Knowledge creation and transfer

S/N	Research Statement	SA	A	D	Std.Dev	Mean	Rank
1	Older family members (e.g., grandparents/parents) share valuable traditional knowledge (e.g., cultural practices, life skills) that younger generations find useful in the business	62 51.7%	45 37.5%	9 7.5%	4 3.3%	3.38	1
2	Younger family members (e.g., children/teens) contribute technological/digital skills that help older generations adapt to modern tools (e.g., smartphones, apps) or innovation in the smooth running of business	34 28.3%	77 64.2%	9 7.5%	-	3.21	2

3.	Differences in education/professional backgrounds among family members enhance collective problem-solving in family business	41 34.2%	32 27.0%	18 15%	29 24.0%	2.71	4
4.	Generational gaps sometimes create barriers to effective knowledge sharing in family business	55 45.8%	23 19.2%	37 30.8%	5 4.2%	3.07	3

Source: Field data, 2025

The study also sought to ascertain the intergenerational tensions that impede knowledge sharing in family business. With a mean score of 3.36 and 2.85 respectively, findings indicate that intergenerational tensions are manifested through power dynamics, particularly in instances where the older generation exerts dominant control over decision-making processes, as well as through resistance by senior family members to the adoption of novel ideas or approaches proposed by younger generations.

Table 4: Intergenerational tensions impeding knowledge sharing (N=120)

S/N	Research Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Rank
1	Older family members resist the adoption of new ideas or methods suggested by younger generations	45 37.5%	27 22.5%	33 27.5%	15 13.2%	2.85	2
2	Younger family members dismiss traditional knowledge shared by elders as outdated or irrelevant	33 27.5%	42 35%	35 29.2%	10 8.3%	2.82	3
3.	Conflicts arising from generational differences discourage open discussions about family business practices or values	41 34.2%	27 22.5%	33 13.2%	19 15.8%	2.75	4
4.	Power dynamics (e.g., elders dominating decisions) limit equal participation in family knowledge exchange	62 51.7%	39 32.5%	19 15.8%	-	3.36	1

Source: Field data, 2025

Discussion of Findings

Regarding the first objective of this study, findings indicate that knowledge is transferred in family business using majorly mentoring and coaching. This is complemented with observation and apprenticeship, storytelling and informal interactions. The findings of this study are in agreement with Mansouri and Moufdi (2025). Family business support use of mentoring, coaching and informal interactions for knowledge creation and transfer, in conformity with the socialisation process of the knowledge creation transfer cycle. Knowledge generated and shared in family business is usually tacit, difficult to document, informally shared, and concentrated among business owners and initiators across generations (Bell, and Pham, 2021). According to Idris, et al., (2025), knowledge sharing improves intergenerational relationships. One of the ways to ensure the continuity of family business is through knowledge transfer (Botero, et al., 2022).

Some scholars note that learning by doing remains a central way for transferring tacit knowledge (Pipatanantakurn and Ractham, 2022). Mentoring is used as a knowledge creation and transfer method. This provides the avenue for establishing teaching relationships. Informal interactions serve as communities of practice. Utrilla and Torraleja (2013) found a direct relationship between mentoring and coaching and the success of family businesses.

Family businesses in Nigeria struggle to successfully apply KM practices due to a high degree of reliance on oral knowledge (Ugochukwu et al., 2022; Adegbite and Adetunji, 2024; Ibrahim and Bello, 2024; Okafor and Eze, 2024). This suggests that younger generation in family business needs to document the tacit knowledge either by written format or audio or visual format, and ensures proper storage of such knowledge to ensure its preservation.

The second objective of this study uncovers the family dynamics that support knowledge transfer. Findings showed that older family members share valuable tacit knowledge with the younger generations while the younger ones bring technological innovation and digital skills. This finding corroborates Rondi, et al. (2021) and Pavlov, et al. (2024). These findings suggest that older family members play a significant role in transferring valuable traditional and experiential knowledge, which supports business continuity and decision-making. Appleton et al. (2025) argue that family business should be willing to embrace digital innovation. The digital innovation is usually conceived and facilitated by the younger generation who have the digital and technological skills necessary to facilitate smoother business operations necessary for making businesses to remain relevant in a modern environment.

The last objective of this study examined intergenerational tensions that impede knowledge sharing in family business. Findings showed that power dynamics - for instance, where the older generation dominates decisions, impede equal participation in knowledge transfer. This finding is in congruence with Eddleston, et al. (2012). Intergenerational differences arise from variations in beliefs, attitudes, because they were born in different years and grew up in different settings (Mannheim, 1998). Although family businesses benefit from intergenerational knowledge exchange, they must deliberately manage differences in age, perspectives, and backgrounds to enhance knowledge creation and transfer processes. This scenario often leads to underutilisation of younger family members' skills in the business. To overcome these obstacles, family firms might need to implement more inclusive initiatives that foster respect between generations and establish welcoming environments that promote fair and transparent involvement in decision-making and information exchange. Moreover, the findings of this study revealed that the older generation resists the adoption of new ideas or methods suggested by younger generations in family business. This finding corroborates Zaidin et al. (2025), Gil et al. (2025), and Subhani et al. (2026). Through the use of technology and innovation from the younger generation, family businesses are better able to adopt digital marketing strategies such as social media marketing involving use of Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp to reach new customers and expand their online presence.

Conclusion

This study concludes that knowledge creation and transfer is essential in family businesses not just for the purpose of succession but to improve intergenerational relationships that could foster continuity even after the demise of the business owner. Generational differences in family businesses could create significant barriers to effective knowledge sharing, as variations in values, communication styles, and openness to change often hinder the transfer of critical skills and experience between older and younger members. Therefore, family businesses are to embrace structured yet flexible knowledge sharing initiatives, such as dialogue sessions to overcome generational gaps arising from differences in culture, age, experience, perception and innovation. The limitation of this study is that data was collected from family business owners situated in one local government area. Further studies should examine knowledge management practices among family business owners from other local government areas in both formal and informal sectors and in other contextual settings in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

- i. To enhance knowledge management practices, family businesses should document tacit knowledge. This ensures that both tacit (experience-based) and explicit (recorded) information are effectively preserved and shared.
- ii. Low-cost tools such as notebooks, checklists, shared folders, and brief monthly review meetings can help preserve knowledge created and shared in family business without disrupting daily operations.
- iii. Formal conflict resolution protocols e.g. family meetings, mediation by a trusted party, clear agreement on leadership role, and record keeping should be embraced in resolving generational differences in a constructive manner.
- iv. Digital upskilling is necessary for older generations to close the gap between technology and tradition.

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